

Supplementary Crystallographic Information

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DHG

DHG nanocrystals suitable for electron diffraction analysis were grown from ethanol (Figure S1a). Electron diffraction experiments were performed using a Glacios transmission electron microscope (Thermo Fisher) equipped with the EPU-D (Thermo Fisher) module operating in continuous-rotation mode. The sample was cooled to liquid nitrogen temperature within the TEM.

DHG forms thin, needle-like crystals with a lateral width of 100-200 nm and a length of a few microns. The crystals exhibited poor crystallinity and were extremely radiation-sensitive. Data were collected at an electron dose of 8.3 e/nm^2 per frame. The first diffraction frame had a resolution of approximately 1.3 \AA , but already after eight consecutive frames, the pattern resolution degraded to 3 \AA . These data could not be used for direct methods structure analysis. We attempted to merge multiple datasets and determine the structure using molecular replacement, but this approach was also unsuccessful.

The unit cell was orthorhombic with the lattice parameters of 5.83, 25.98, and 50.16 \AA . The volume of the unit cell was 7597.4 \AA^3 . The expected molecular volume of DHG was 578.9 \AA^3 (Hofmann, 2002), indicating that the unit cell could accommodate 14 molecules. Extinctions were observed along the main crystallographic axes (Figure S1b), suggesting the $P2_12_12_1$ space group with $Z=4$. This implies that there could be three independent molecules in the asymmetric unit, with the remaining unit cell volume filled with solvent or voids.

No diffuse scattering associated with stacking faults was observed; instead, high mosaicity of the crystals was noted.

Figure S1. TEM image of DHG nanocrystals (a) and the [001] crystallographic zone. Extinctions along the vertical [100] axis, corresponding to a 2_1 screw axis, can be detected.

Cu DHG complex

In an attempt to grow nanocrystals of DHG suitable for electron diffraction analysis, we placed a copper TEM grid into an ethanol DHG solution, punched a small hole in the plastic lid of the glass vial, and let the solvent evaporate slowly. To our surprise, two weeks after, the solvent evaporated and large green crystals grew on the grid (Figure S2). The TEM grid was destroyed.

One of the crystals, deemed optically suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction, was selected for crystallographic analysis. Additional experimental and crystallographic details are available in the CIF

file (CSD deposition number 2376486).

Figure S2. Optical microscopy image of a copper TEM grid after exposure to an ethanol suspension of DHG for approximately 2 weeks.

The crystal structure represents a copper complex of the deprotonated DHG. The affinity of DHG for copper was sufficiently strong to etch the TEM copper grid.

The asymmetric unit of the crystal structure (space group type $P2_12_12_1$) contains a single copper ion coordinated by two independent molecules of monodeprotonated DHG. The monodeprotonated DHG acts as a bidentate ligand coordinating in a typical 1,3-dionate fashion via two oxygen atoms, forming a slightly distorted square planar oxygen

atom ligand set around the central metal ion (Figure S3a). Copper-oxygen distances of 1.924(2) Å, 1.903(2) Å, 1.913(2) Å and 1.907(2) Å are found. The O–Cu–O including oxygen atoms of the same ligand molecule are with 93.55(8)° and 93.39(7)° significantly larger than the respective inter-ligand O–Cu–O angles of 84.50(7)° and 88.58(7)°. None of the four discussed oxygen ligand atoms deviate more than 0.112(2) Å from the mean plane [Cu1, O1, O2, O1a, O2a]. Additionally, the structure contains two independent partly occupied water molecules with 0.40(1) (O5) and 0.42(1) (O6) site occupation, respectively. One molecule (O5) is coordinated to the copper ion in an apical position, with a copper-oxygen distance of 2.379(6) Å, rendering the coordination environment at the copper ion distorted square pyramidal. The other molecule is not coordinated to copper ion but participates in a hydrogen bond network.

The two symmetry-independent monodeprotonated DHG ligands have a very similar conformation (Figure S3b). A slightly different, but still comparable conformation is realized in chlorotonil A and chlorotonil B crystal structures (Figure S4).

Figure S3. Coordination of copper ion by two symmetry independent DHG molecules (a); overlay of geometries of two independent molecules (b).

Figure S4. Overlay of molecular conformation of DHG with the molecular conformation of chlorotonil A molecule (a) and chlorotonil B molecule (b). In both cases, the carbon atoms of the DHG molecule are shown in grey.

Al DHG complex

Al-DHG crystals were obtained from an ethanol suspension of DHG with aluminium oxide powder. Very thin, hexagonally shaped, transparent crystals formed on the inner sides of the glass vial (Figure S5). For diffraction data collection, crystals were harvested onto a nylon loop, cryo-protected with 10% (v/v) (R,R)-2,3-butanediol, and flash-cooled in liquid N₂. Data collection was carried out at 100 K on beamline P11 of the PETRA III storage ring at the Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY, Hamburg, Germany). HDF files were converted to CBF using the *eiger2cbf* tool. The CBF files were then imported and processed in CrysAlisPro.

Figure S5. Optical microscopy image of Al DHG crystals.

Al DHG crystallizes in a hexagonal $P6_3$ space group with two monodeprotonated DHG ligands in the asymmetric unit. Three ligands coordinate with the aluminum atom, forming a regular octahedral coordination around the metal. The two symmetrically independent ligands have essentially the same conformation and form two symmetry independent $AlDHG_3$ complexes in the unit cell.

The CSD deposition code of the structure is 2376487.

Co DHG complex

Nanocrystals suitable for electron diffraction measurements were obtained from an ethanol suspension of DGH and metallic cobalt. The crystals showed triangular or hexagonal shapes and were sufficiently thin for ED (Figure S6).

The data were collected with EPU-D and saved in MRC and SMV formats. We initially processed the MRC datasets in PETS2 (Palatinus et al., 2019) and noticed that the unit cell parameters and symmetry were identical to those of the Al-DHG complex. This usually implies that the materials are isostructural.

The data resolution was not sufficient to determine the structure using direct methods. We then integrated and merged seven SMV datasets with autoPROC (Vonrhein et al., 2011). The statistical metrics of the obtained merged dataset are shown in Table S1. The original electron diffraction data and the merged dataset can be found on Zenodo doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13268606

Figure S6. Crystals of Co-DHG used for ED data collection.

Table S1. Results of autoPROC processing of Co-DHG electron diffraction data

Isotropic data analysis:			
Spacegroup			P63
Cell parameters		14.12 14.12 44.80	
		90.0 90.0 120.0	
Wavelength [Å]			0.02508
	Overall	Inner Shell	Outer Shell
Low resolution limit	12.228	12.228	1.093
High resolution limit	1.074	2.903	1.074
Rmerge (all I+ & I-)	0.508	0.419	2.903
Rmeas (all I+ & I-)	0.517	0.426	3.515
Rpim (all I+ & I-)	0.094	0.077	1.940
Total number of observations	48131	3407	205
Total number unique	2101	111	85
Mean(I)/sd(I)	6.9	17.0	0.7
Completeness	94.5	95.7	76.6
Multiplicity	22.9	30.7	2.4
CC(1/2)	0.985	0.979	0.478
Anomalous completeness	91.9	94.4	47.7
Anomalous multiplicity	11.9	15.8	1.6
CC(ano)	0.174	0.201	-0.073
DANO /sd(DANO)	0.701	0.861	0.690

We converted the MTZ file to ASCII (CIF format) in CCP4i via Reflection Data Utilities and attempted structure solution with direct methods, which still didn't work. Finally, we turned to molecular replacement as implemented in Phaser. As the search fragments, we used two DGH molecules in the conformation extracted from the Al-DHG crystal structure. The final solution had a TFZ of 7.1 and an LLG of 132. The positions of cobalt evolved in the difference Fourier map (Figure S7) and were populated with 1/3 Co atoms. The structure was subsequently refined in Coot.

As expected, the two crystal structures—Al-DHG and Co-DHG—were essentially the same. Therefore, we decided against the separate publication of the molecular replacement structure analysis of the Co-DHG complex.

Despite the relatively low impact of this analysis within the context of this publication, the successful molecular replacement structure determination of Co-DHG from electron diffraction data once again demonstrates the potential of alternative phasing methods for electron diffraction data with low resolution.

Figure S7. Results of the molecular replacement structure solution of Co-DHG from electron diffraction data. The position of Co atoms in the middle of the clusters is evident. Two crystallographically independent clusters are shown in cyan and magenta. The $2mF_o - DF_c$ maps are contoured at 1.3σ above the mean, and the densities are carved at 2 \AA .

On the crystal structures of Cu, Al and Co DHG complexes

In the crystal structures, monodeprotonated DHG molecules coordinate metal ions through their 1,3-dionate units. In the Cu-DHG crystal structures, two molecules coordinate a single copper atom (Figure S8). In the Co and Al crystal structures, three DHG molecules coordinate a single metal atom (Figure S8).

The height of the complexes (measured from the top to bottom carbon atoms) is approximately 12.4 \AA . These complexes have highly hydrophobic surfaces. One could speculate whether these clusters might integrate into the hydrophobic environment of a lipid membrane. Although the height of the cluster would not be sufficient to penetrate the entire membrane, it could create an opening at the surface of the membrane. Deeper within the membrane, the aliphatic chains might react on this opening and potentially form a channel for metal ion transport through the membrane.

Figure S8. Conformations of the dimer and tripod clusters formed within the DHG – metal complexes.

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References:

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